

Style at Your Fingertips: Neural Style Transfer via Telegram Bot

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Abstract - Neural Style Transfer (NST) allows artistic image conversion through content and style fusion, but existing implementations are typically resource-intensive, time-consuming, and technical. It thus remains inaccessible to non-technical users. To address these concerns, this project introduces a lightweight Telegram bot that performs real-time style transfer using a pre-trained Adaptive Instance Normalization (AdaIN) model. AdaIN allows rapid high-quality output with reduced computation and hence can be used on a daily basis. The bot provides a simple user interface to translate artistic styles onto their photos without installing advanced software or requiring technical expertise. The approach is to simplify NST and make it more convenient and rapid to use.

Keywords—Neural Style Transfer, Tensor Flow Hub, Telegram Bot, Deep Learning, Image Processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Neural Style Transfer is a deep learning technique that enables the transfer of an artistic style to a given content image. Precursor work by Gatys et al.[1] propose during CNN architectures similar to VGG16 and VGG19 for retrieving content and style representations separately. These rely on the reconstruction of images using iterative optimization techniques, which are obviously computationally expensive and time-consuming to execute.

In further developments of NST, efficiency and scalability have come to the foreground. Simonyan

and Zisserman [2] successfully showed the usage of deep convolutional networks in large-scale image recognition, upon which NST has been based. Further, the introduction of perceptual losses in real-time style transfer by Johnson et al. [4] reduced the computationally expensive process to a manageable level. Here, feed forward networks were employed to apply stylization in one pass, achieving real-time artistic transformations.

The most significant contribution in NST has been adaptive instance normalization (AdaIN) by Huang and Belongie[5], enabling real-time arbitrary style transfer. Traditional approach es rely on pre-trained models with fixed styles, but

AdaIN adjusts feature statistics dynamically to achieve high-quality stylization with minimal computational resources. In the same context, Ulyanov et al.[6] considered instance normalization as a key component for rapid stylization and further improved the performance.

Recent developments have incorporated GANs into NST. Ledig et al. [8] applied GANs to super-resolution tasks, showing the feasibility of using GANs in artistic transformations. Jing et al.[9] also gave a detailed overview of NST techniques, showing the development from traditional CNN-based methods to more advanced architectures such as transformers and GANs. Karras et al. [10] introduced a style-based generator architecture for GANs, increasing the photo-realism and further diversity of stylized image

The document contains Section II (Literature Survey), which compares different approaches to NST such as CNN-based, feed forward, AdaIN, GAN, and transformer-based models with their shortcomings and justifying the effectiveness of Telegram bot. Section III (Methodology) speaks about the architecture of the system, i.e., Telegram bot interface, NST processing module, and response mechanism, describing the flow of data from image uploading to application of style transfer. Section IV (Experiment and Results) verifies the model's performance through artistic transformations, measuring processing time, preservation of quality, and user satisfaction. Section V (Future Scope) recommends AI-generated styles, enhanced model adaptability, and style fetching automation. Section VI(Conclusion)summarizes the research, citing the Telegram bot's efficiency, real-time functioning, and ease of use, and recommends innovations such as AI-generated styles and enhanced model flexibility. Section VII (References) identifies key research papers that validate the study.

ADVANTAGE OF NEURAL STYLE TRANSFER OVER TRADITIONAL APPROACHES

Neural Style Transfer (NST) has several advantages compared to traditional image processing and artistic transformation techniques:

Efficiency and Speed. Most traditional approaches depend on manual artistic rendering or heavy iterative optimization. NST allows for real-time transformation using deep learning techniques.

Automation and Scalability. Compared to manual approaches, in NST, style transfer is automated that may be applied at a high scale and without human intervention.

Flexible style transfer: This means that the NST can adjust itself to change according to several styles dynamically and, therefore is much more versatile than rule-based transformations.

Reduction in Computation Complexity: Use of pre- trained models from Tensor Flow Hub maintains the quality while reducing the computation complexity.

Less Distortion to the Content: Unlike traditional filters and transformations, the NST avoids the distortion of content in images by preserving their original content in terms of objects.

Coupling with AI Technology: NST could be combined with GAN, transformers, or reinforcement learning so as to bring performance and flexibility into the framework.

Improved realism: Modern variants of NST including adaptive instance normalization and perceptual loss functions would generate more appealing and natural effects compared to current digital effects.

Low Computational Cost: Due to recent improvements in deep learning, optimized NST models can provide high-quality transformations with low computational resources, thereby being useful in real-time applications.

Leveraging all of these advantages, NST has turned out to be a very strong tool for artistic creativity, social media applications, and automated content generation in multiple industries.

II. LITERATURESURVEY

Different approaches have been developed for Neural Style Transfer, with their advantages and disadvantages. The traditional approaches in NST use convolutional neural networks, mostly VGG16 and VGG19, requiring huge computational resources and iterative optimization. Real-time applications are henceforth difficult [1]. The approach of the Telegram bot implemented uses a pre-trained TensorFlow Hub model, greatly reducing the requirements of computation, which makes the real-time application of style transfer possible.

Traditional CNN-based NST (e.g., VGG16, VGG19) :

Gatys et al.[1] Initially used deep convolutional neural networks like VGG16 and VGG19 to obtain content and style independently. Though effective, they are associated with iterative optimization, which is expensive in terms of computation and unrealistic for real-time applications.

Feed forward NST:

Johnson et al. [4] proposed feed forward neural networks to facilitate faster stylization. Such models reduce computational time but require separate models for each style, which hampers flexibility and scalability.

Adaptive Instance Normalization (AdaIN):

Huang and Belongie [5] proposed AdaIN, allowing arbitrary style transfer by matching feature statistics. Although AdaIN drastically decreases computation and facilitates dynamic styles, it does not have user-friendly deployment frameworks and hence is unavailable to non-experts.

GAN-Based NST:

GANs increase realism and style diversity, as demonstrated by Ledig et al. [8] and Karras et al. [10]. GAN-based models are challenging to train and need huge datasets, and high inference times are not mobile or chat bot-based application-friendly.

Transformer-Based NST (ViT):

Existing studies examine transformer models for style transfer, offering improved attention mechanisms and adaptability. Despite these advantages, they are compute intensive and have not yet been successfully integrated into lightweight real-time applications like messaging apps.

Software Dependence and Usability Problems:

Most NST applications require specialized technical knowledge or standalone software, making them out of reach for ordinary users. There is a clear usability gap in current solutions.

Our Contribution:

This eliminates these shortcomings by integrating a pre-trained AdaIN-based NST model inside a Telegram bot, which eliminates the necessity for installation, retraining of the model, or technical knowledge.

“Real-time artistic style transfer

Efficient processing independent of a GPU

Multi-user support via the Telegram API

Ease of access for non-technical users with an approachable messaging platform”

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is the combination of Neural Style Transfer integrated with a Telegram bot so that one can apply styles to their images in real time. Methodology involved in the development is divided into the following steps:

1. System Architecture: There are three major components of the system.

Telegram Bot Interface: Handling all user activities and uploading the images

NST Processing Module: Applying artistic transformations through a pre-trained Tensor Flow Hub model. **Response System:** Outputs the styled image to the client. This module uses a server-side implementation in handling requests from clients, transforming images, and returning responses to clients in a very efficient way.

2. Pre-trained Style Transfer Neural Network:

We apply the Tensor Flow Hub arbitrary image stylization model with Adaptive Instance Normalization. Such an implementation style transfer model assures the following conditions: Computational cost is lesser than the case of VGG- based models High quality styling with a shorter processing time Arbitrary styling without needing for retraining

3. Data Flow & Processing: User Uploads an Image–The Telegram bot receives an image and a chosen artistic style.

Image Preprocessing–The input image is resized and normalized to be compatible with the NST model.

Style Transfer Execution–The model extracts content and style features using AdaIN and generates the stylized output.

Image Post processing–The transformed image is converted back into a format to be displayed.

Output: The final output is provided to the user in the form of the Telegram bot.

4. Deployment & Scalability:

Multiple requests from a large number of users are serviced in parallel. It is built on a cloud-based server Telegram's API ensures smooth flow of interaction. It runs fluently without depending on local computing by GPU.

This methodology ensures that the resulting transformation system is efficient, scalable, and user-friendly: advanced techniques in NST are conveyed to a larger audience through an interface of an easy-to-use chat bot.

Fig3.1: Work flow of NST

1. Image Selection & Upload

A user selects an image from a device and uploads it to Telegram. In Telegram we accept format is JPEG.

2. Server-Side Processing

Once uploaded, the server will do the further optimization with respect to image dimensions, encode it again and cache it in order to serve it to various users in the most efficient manner.

3. User Download & View

The receiver downloads and views the image by opening it. If they need to save or forward the image, they are given this ability. If being sent as a document, it will be downloaded uncompressed and at full resolution.

The streamlined nature in the processing of images in the Telegram application makes it user-friendly by providing it with fast and easy sharing over images while giving the option to transfer an uncompressed file. Hence, it is preferred over others.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

In order to assess the performance of the suggested Neural Style Transfer (NST) Telegram bot, a sequence of experiments were performed with multiple content images and styles. A diverse set of inputs like landscapes, portraits, and abstracts were used to test model generalization.

1. Experimental Setup

Images were sent through the Telegram bot interface in JPEG format. Each image was accompanied by a selected style image (e.g., "Monalisa", "Picasso"). The stylization was done in real time by the system, which is based on Tensor Flow Hub's AdaIN-based pre-trained model. Performance metrics used include:

Processing Time (average 2–4 seconds)

There were several tests in artistic styles to consider adaptability and efficiency of the model. Processing time along with user experience was measured as a performance factor.

RESULTS

Fig4.1 illustrates the original input image used for testing stylization.

Fig4.2:TheMona LisaArt is a style reference image

Fig4.6:Antelopecanyon

Fig4.3:OutputForMonalisaArt

Fig4.7:OutputforAntelopecanyon

Fig4.4:ThePicassoArt

Fig4.5:OutputforPicassoArt

V. FUTURESCOPE& CONCLUSION

We introduce an easy-to-use Neural Style Transfer (NST) solution through a Telegram bot for real-time artistic image transformation. The system, employing a pre-trained AdaIN model from Tensor Flow Hub, eschews computationally intensive VGG-based approaches and provides easy usage for non-technical users. It effectively maintains content while applying varied styles. Challenges are addressing high-resolution images, accommodating additional styles, and sustaining performance in multi-user scenarios. Future developments will include AI-modeled styles, text-based style instructions, and transformer-based modeling for better coherence of style. Although it lacks flexibility such as fixed resolution and internet reliance, this method enables NST to be more practical and accessible to people.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] L.A.Gatys, A.S.Ecker, and M.Bethge, "A Neural Algorithm of Artistic Style," *Journal of Vision Research*, 2016.
- [2] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, "Very Deep Convolutional Networks for Large-Scale Image Recognition," *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2015.
- [3] C.Szegedy, W.Liu, Y.Jia, et al., "Going Deeper with Convolutions," *Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2015.
- [4] J. Johnson, A. Alahi, and L. Fei-Fei, "Perceptual Losses for Real-Time Style Transfer and Super-Resolution," *European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV)*, 2016.
- [5] X.Huang and S.Belongie, "Arbitrary Style Transfer in Real-Time with Adaptive Instance Normalization," *International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 2017.
- [6] D.Ulyanov, A.Vedaldi, and V. Lempitsky, "Instance Normalization: The Missing Ingredient for Fast Stylization," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1607.08022*, 2016.
- [7] Google AI, "Tensor Flow Hub: Arbitrary Image Stylization," Available at: <https://tfhub.dev/google/magenta/arbitrary-image-stylization-v1-256/2>.
- [8] C.Ledig, L.Theis, F.Huszar, et al., "Photo-Realistic Single Image Super Resolution Using a Generative Adversarial Network," *CVPR*, 2017.
- [9] Y.Jing, Y.Yang, Z.Feng, et al., "Neural Style Transfer: A Review," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 2020.
- [10] T. Karras, S. Laine, and T. Aila, "A Style-Based Generator Architecture for Generative Adversarial Networks," *Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2019.